

SOFTWARE AND METHODOLOGICAL SUPPORT OF INCLUSIVE EDUCATION IN A PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTION

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Abstract: A student with disabilities is an individual who has deficiencies in physical and (or) psychological development, confirmed by the psychological-medical-pedagogical commission and preventing education without creating special conditions. The article discusses some aspects of the software and methodological support of inclusive education in a preschool educational institution.

Key words: Social adaptation of children, difficulties in adaptation, vocational training, educational activities, socio-pedagogical research.

Аннотация: Обучающийся с ограниченными возможностями здоровья – физическое лицо, имеющее недостатки в физическом и (или) психологическом развитии, подтвержденные психолого-медико-педагогической комиссией и препятствующие получению образования без создания специальных условий. В статье рассмотрены некоторые аспекты программно-методическое обеспечение инклюзивного образования в дошкольном образовательном учреждении.

Ключевые слова: Социальная адаптация детей, затруднения адаптации, профессиональная подготовка, образовательная деятельность, социально-педагогические исследования.

The implementation of the full development, education and social adaptation of a child with disabilities becomes fully possible only in a situation where all the necessary conditions are provided. In this case, an inclusive educational environment will correspond to the opportunities and resources available to a child with disabilities for full-fledged “advancement” in the educational program in the

dynamics corresponding to his abilities. At the same time, the educational needs of other children included in the inclusive process will be met in the same way.

Inclusive education is the provision of equal access to education for all students, taking into account the diversity of special educational needs and individual opportunities.

A student with disabilities (HIA) is an individual who has deficiencies in physical and (or) psychological development, confirmed by the psychological-medical-pedagogical commission and preventing education without creating special conditions. The determination of the conditions for obtaining education is entrusted to the psychological, medical and pedagogical commissions (PMPC). Within the framework of Moscow legislation, a normative act regulating the education of persons with disabilities, including determining the necessary conditions for its implementation.

The most generalized requirements for the conditions for obtaining education for children with disabilities are reflected in the Draft of a special federal state standard for primary school education for children with disabilities (N.N. Malofeev, O.S. Nikolskaya, O.I. Kukushkina, 2010). It says that it is necessary to give an integral (generalized) description of the set of conditions necessary for the implementation of the relevant educational programs, structured by areas of resource support. At the same time, it is noted that such a system of requirements should include specific components in accordance with the special educational needs of children with disabilities in general and for each category of deviant development separately.

Ultimately, the Project notes, the integrative result of the implementation of these requirements should be: creation of an environment adequate to general and special educational needs, physically and emotionally comfortable for a child with disabilities, open to his parents (legal representatives); guaranteeing the preservation and strengthening of the physical and psychological health of students.

The third stage is to create a friendly and healthy environment in the process of raising children with disabilities in a team with healthy peers, increasing the legal

literacy of parents, and ensuring compliance with the provisions of the Convention on the Rights of the Child. We need to introduce inclusive education in general preschool institutions. In specialized preschools, children with disabilities do not adapt to the social environment, they feel isolated from society. When introducing inclusion in preschool education, problems were identified that impede the normal course of the process. Unfortunately, there are many of them. These are insufficient conditions for the development and rehabilitation of children with various forms of disability, the lack of qualified personnel, as well as cooperation between general organizations and institutions of special education. Therefore, it is important to form the spirit of friendship, humanism, care and attention in the children's team. Prepare a child with disabilities for a trouble-free education in an inclusive school, create inclusive groups for children with mild disabilities and the opportunity for them to receive pre-school education. Demonstrate to the general public the humanity of the goals and principles of inclusive education and, most importantly, stand up for the rights of the child. It is obvious that in the life of the current pupils of the specialized boarding school No. 36 of the Kyzyltepa district with mental retardation, this was the first public recognition. Hilola Tokhtamurodova, a 3rd year student of the Tashkent Institute of Textile and Light Industry, the author of the "Peace with You" project, left with such an impression after meeting with rural children. As part of the first youth festival "IdeaFEST: from ideas to implementation", a participant from Uzbekistan won a grant from the main organizer in the amount of 12 thousand euros. In our country, "Peace be with you" started in December 2020. As part of the project, it is planned to visit all regions of the republic and conduct three-day trainings on manual creativity for children with Down syndrome and autism. The first workshops on quilling, stained glass, decoupage and ikebana were held in Gulistan, Jizzakh, Samarkand region with the participation of 85 children with Down syndrome and autism. Project participants in each region were awarded diplomas and colorful gifts. In the Navoi region, 25 pupils with disabilities from the Kyzyltepe boarding school were taught to work with papier-mâché and decoupage. Children studied with great interest and pleasure, did very beautiful work, and later admired

and rejoiced at their work. Happiness and delight in their eyes delighted every member of the “Peace be with you” team.

“Perhaps we would have continued to live like this, knowing nothing about “sunny” children, if it were not for the will of the case that changed us and the world around us,” says the author of the “Peace be with you” project Hilola Tokhtamurodova.

So, in 2017, a woman brought her 16-year-old daughter with Down syndrome to her, a teacher of needlework in one of the cultural centers. The girl's mother was very worried and wanted her child to be taught the craft. Hilola undertook to teach at home.

As it turned out, the girl really likes to draw. And with each lesson, she progressed, showing imagination, the ability to independently think over the drawing and decorate it to her liking. This circumstance inspired the young mentor to create a project aimed at developing creativity in children with Down syndrome and autism. After all, there are many examples when a person with such a diagnosis achieves success, creates a family, gets a profession and lives an ordinary happy life, like all healthy people. According to H. Tokhtamurodova, the children - participants of the project - made her understand that life is a movement forward. You should not be disappointed and stop there. You need to study the world around you and people more deeply.

Thus, it is the child's special educational needs that determine the need for recommendations on the creation of one or more of the listed conditions when he is included in the educational process.

1 In describing the conditions and requirements for organizing an adaptive educational environment, the approaches and materials of the Draft Special Federal State Standard for Primary School Education (N.N. Malofeev, O.S. Nikolskaya, O.I. Kukushkina, 2010) were used.

2 Adapted educational program - an educational program adapted for the training of persons with disabilities, taking into account the peculiarities of their

psychophysical development, individual capabilities and, if necessary, providing correction of developmental disorders and social adaptation of these persons.

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